

Italy

3rd wave survey - 2023

Age group

Data collection was carried out in **4 schools** and involved **1323 students**.

Gender distribution

SES distribution

On average, adolescents reported **knowing very well** how to do 62% of the activities on digital **communication and interaction**, but **only 31%** of the activities related to **information and navigation**.

Self-reported performance on skills increases with age for all groups of digital skills. Boys and girls differ on every group of skills: boys had on average 65% of technological and operational skills compared to girls who had 49% of these skills at a high level. The same trend applies to information and navigation skills (boys 36%, girls 25%), and content creation and production skills (boys 34%, girls 28%). Girls reported a higher level of communication and interaction skills than boys (62% vs. 59%)

Knowledge items*

* Respondents answered a set of questions designed to measure their actual knowledge about how the internet and digital technologies work.

The average of correct answers to digital knowledge is 56%. The percentage of correct answers related to digital knowledge is slightly higher for boys (57%, girls 55%) and increases with age.

How digital literacy levels increase in adolescents who participated in three waves (349)?

In 2023, the **communication and interaction** dimension had the highest level of high digital literacy (on 63% of the skills and knowledge elements) but stayed the same compared to 2022. The **information and navigation** dimension, in turn, showed an increase compared to 2021.

Communication and interaction

Content creation and production

Information and navigation

Digital literacy* is a combination of digital skills and knowledge regarding how the internet and digital technologies work.

*The levels of digital literacy are a merger of self-reported high-level skills and the correct answer on the knowledge items. For technological and operational skills digital literacy could not be accounted for due to a lack of knowledge items.

Digital literacy increases with age. Boys present higher digital literacy levels (49%) in comparison to girls (43%).